

at δ 0.90 (6 protons) and δ 1.25 (58 protons) indicating it to be a saturated aliphatic hydrocarbon. The identity of this hydrocarbon as *n*-hentriacontane has been confirmed by m.m.p., Co - TLC and CO - IR with authentic specimen of the compound.

Elution of the column with benzene gave a white solid, m.p. 125-30° which responds to positive Liebermann-Burchardt test for sterol. The mass spectrum of the compound registered two molecular ion peaks at m/e 414 and 412 respectively along with other peaks at m/e 396 (414-H₂O), 394 (412-H₂O), 255 (396-side chain C₁₀H₂₁ or 394-side chain C₁₀H₁₉). These data reveals that this compound is a mixture of β -sitosterol and stigmasterol. Further separation of this mixture was not possible due to paucity of the material.

The fraction eluted with benzene yielded a white solid crystallising from methanol as colourless needles, m.p. 126°, $\nu_{\max}^{\text{KBr}}$ 1725, 1160 cm⁻¹ (ester-carbonyl). It responds positive to Liebermann-Burchardt test for sterol and was identified as β -sitosterol acetate from the mass spectrum [M⁺ 456, m/e 414 (M-CH₃CO), 396 (M-CH₃COOH), 255 (396-C₁₀H₂₁)], m.m.p. determination, Co - TLC and CO - IR with authentic sample of β -sitosterol acetate.

The benzene extract on chromatographic resolution afforded only β -sitosterol.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. B. C. Das, Institut de Chime des Substance Naturelles, France, R.S.I.C., Bose Institute, Calcutta for mass spectral analyses and Dr. M. Chakraborty, Department of Chemistry, University College, Cardiff, U.K. for NMR and IR spectra. The financial assistance from UGC is also gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. "Medicinal Plants of India", Vol. 1, I.C.M.R., 1976, p. 352.
2. D. S. BHAKUNI, M. L. DHAR, M. M. DHAR, B. N. DHAWAN and B. N. MEHROTRA, *Indian J. Exptl. Biol.*, 1969, 7, 250.
3. S. R. BHATTACHARJEE and A. CHATTERJEE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 39, 276.
4. T. SUNDARARAMAIAH, S. K. RAMRAJ, K. LAKSHMAN RAO and V. VIMALABAI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 638.
5. R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYAR and I. C. CHOPRA, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", C.S.I.R., 1956, p. 256.
6. N. K. BASU and G. B. SINGH, *Indian J. Pharm.*, 1944, 6, 71.
7. T. P. GHOSE and S. KRISHNA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 634.

8. N. K. BASU and G. B. SINGH, *Quart. J. Pharm.*, 1947, 20, 136.
9. N. K. BASU, G. K. RAY and N. K. DE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 24, 358.
10. A. BANERJI, M. S. CHADHA and V. G. MALSHIT, *Phytochemistry*, 1969, 8, 511.
11. G. S. GUPTA and K. BEHARI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 367.
12. G. A. QUAZI, S. K. OSMAN and M. R. SUBBARAM, *J. Oil Technol. Ass. India*, 1973, 5, 14.
13. (Mrs.) V. JOSHI, J. R. MERCHANT, V. V. NADKARNY, N. KRISHNAN and D. D. VAGHANI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, 12, 226.
14. H. E. AUDIER, R. BEUGELMANS and B. C. DAS, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1966, 4341.

Studies on Carbohydrates and Amino Acids of Some Non-Cultivated Leguminous Seeds

SANTOSH KUMAR KATIYAR
and

GOVIND SINGH NIRANJAN

Department of Chemistry, Davanand Vedic (P. G.) College,
Orai (U. P.)

Manuscript received 28 March 1980, revised 30 July 1980,
accepted 29 October 1980

PRELIMINARY analysis for proximate principles of nine non-cultivated leguminous seeds of *Cassia fistula*, *C. occidentalis*, *C. tora*, *Indigofera glandulosa*, *I. hirsuta*, *I. trifoliata*, *Mucuna capitata*, *M. prurita* and *Trigonella occulta* showed them as appreciably rich sources of carbohydrate and proteins, suggested their possible inclusion in animal nutrition. Before including them in dietary, it was considered pertinent to evaluate their adequacy, both qualitative as well as quantitative, as complete proteins with respect to their essential amino acids listed for normal growth and maintenance¹. The total water soluble carbohydrate and total reducing substances were analysed at room temperature (27 ± 3°) as well as at 100°.

Materials and Methods :

Healthy and dry mature seeds were collected, botanically identified, powdered to 100 mesh, defatted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) and employed in all investigations.

The total soluble carbohydrate estimation was carried out by the method of Trevelyn and Harrison² and total soluble reducing substances were estimated by the method of Hagedorn and Jensen as described by Hawk, Oser and Summerson³ and modified by Howden and Kilby⁴. The results are shown in Table 1.

The presence and distribution of soluble carbohydrates like glucose, fructose, sucrose, raffinose,

NOTES

TABLE 1—TOTAL, SOLUBLE CARBOHYDRATE AND TOTAL SOLUBLE REDUCING SUBSTANCES OF SOME WILD LEGUMINOUS SEEDS

(Values are expressed in terms of g glucose/100 g seed powder)

Seeds	Total Carbohydrates		Total Reducing Substances	
	27 ± 3°C	100°C	27 ± 3°C	100°C
1. <i>Cassia fistula</i>	11.80	19.15	4.10	4.15
2. <i>Cassia tora</i>	10.30	18.20	3.85	4.00
3. <i>Cassia occidentalis</i>	11.73	19.21	4.05	4.22
4. <i>Indigofera glandulosa</i>	10.20	17.95	3.05	3.16
5. <i>Indigofera hirsuta</i>	10.10	18.05	4.08	4.17
6. <i>Indigofera trifoliata</i>	9.98	16.88	2.10	2.12
7. <i>Mucuna capitata</i>	15.06	22.31	1.61	1.73
8. <i>Mucuna prurita</i>	18.40	24.68	3.42	3.48

maltose and arabinose were also studied qualitatively of different seeds by using unidimensional paper partition chromatography of Consden, Gordon and Martin⁵. The operation was conducted in an air tight Shandon's chromatographic tank, using solvent system phenol(80%, w/v)-ammonia and ethyl acetate-pyridine-water (12 : 5 : 4). Aniline hydrogen phthalate was used as spray reagent to determine the different sugars as used by Partridge⁶.

Qualitative study of free amino acids were carried out by paper partition chromatography^{5,6,7} and identified by employing the various special spray reagents⁸⁻¹³. Total free amino acids in different seeds were estimated by the method of Rosen¹⁴.

TABLE 2—SOLUBLE FREE SUGARS OF SOME WILD LEGUMINOUS SEEDS

Seeds	Sugars					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
<i>Cassia fistula</i>	+	+	+	+	-	-
<i>Cassia tora</i>	+	-	+	+	-	-
<i>Cassia occidentalis</i>	+	-	+	+	-	-
<i>Indigofera glandulosa</i>	+	-	+	+	+	-
<i>Indigofera hirsuta</i>	+	+	+	+	+	-
<i>Indigofera trifoliata</i>	+	-	+	+	-	+
<i>Mucuna capitata</i>	+	-	+	+	-	-
<i>Mucuna prurita</i>	+	-	+	+	-	+

Sugars : 1. Glucose 2. Fructose 3. Sucrose
4. Raffinose 5. Maltose 6. Arabinose
(+) = Present.
(-) = Absent.

Quantitative estimation of protein-bound individual amino acids were made in the defatted seed powders from which all the free amino acids were removed by repeated extraction with aqueous ethanol (70%, v/v) till the washings became negative to ninhydrin test. Further procedure was employed as previously¹⁵.

Results and Discussion

The results show, when total carbohydrates and total reducing substances were estimated at 100° gave higher values than at room temperature (Table 1). The extraction of higher percentage of carbohydrate at 100° is suggestive of the dissolution of starch and other polysaccharides otherwise insoluble at room temperature as well as possibly due to the release of reducing sugars from di- and

TABLE 3—QUALITATIVE PATTERN AND TOTAL CONTENT OF FREE AMINO ACIDS IN LEGUMINOUS SEEDS

Amino acids	Seeds*								
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
α-alanine	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-
Arginine	+	+	-	+	-	-	+	-	+
Asparagine	+	+	+	-	-	+	-	+	+
Aspartic acid	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Cysteic acid	+	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	-
Cystine	-	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	+
Glutamic acid	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Glutamine	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Glycine	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Histidine	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-
Leucine-isoleucine	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Lysine	+	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	+
Methionine	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	+
Proline	-	+	-	+	-	+	-	-	-
Serine	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Threonine	+	+	+	-	-	+	-	-	-
Tryptophan	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Valine	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	+	+
Total free amino acids g/100 g seeds	0.21	0.33	0.24	0.45	0.37	0.50	0.36	0.27	0.25

+ = Present - = Absent

Seeds* : 1. *Cassia fistula* 2. *Cassia occidentalis* 3. *Cassia tora*
4. *Indigofera glandulosa* 5. *Indigofera hirsuta* 6. *Indigofera trifoliata*
7. *Mucuna capitata* 8. *Mucuna prurita* 9. *Trigonella occulta*

TABLE 4—PROTEIN-BOUND AMINO ACIDS OF POWDERED DEFATTED LEGUMES
(EXPRESSED AS mg GLYCINE PER 100 mg SEED POWDER)

Amino acids	Seeds*								
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
α-alanine	2.74	3.34	1.46	4.14	2.75	3.04	3.52	3.41	1.18
Arginine	—	—	3.58	2.55	1.57	—	2.88	3.26	2.15
Aspartic acid	3.38	3.55	3.56	4.27	2.88	4.01	2.75	2.91	3.51
Cysteic acid	—	—	0.54	—	—	1.01	0.10	0.08	0.03
Cystine	—	—	—	—	0.22	—	—	—	—
Glutamic acid	5.61	4.98	8.95	7.84	5.60	5.63	7.95	8.20	7.55
Glycine	3.02	2.26	2.52	4.16	3.05	3.00	2.32	2.10	2.21
Histidine	1.45	1.32	1.78	1.38	1.65	0.97	1.10	0.82	0.77
Leucine-isoleucine	7.41	6.84	7.14	6.46	6.77	7.44	8.31	7.60	6.42
Lysine	3.46	1.88	6.46	4.36	2.44	2.75	1.55	1.66	2.83
Methionine	0.70	0.46	0.58	—	0.55	1.18	—	—	0.36
Proline**	0.38	0.42	0.44	1.06	2.05	1.06	0.18	0.17	0.31
Serine	3.47	2.30	4.21	2.41	3.10	2.65	1.66	1.95	2.40
Threonine	0.88	1.02	—	—	+	—	—	—	+
Tryptophan	—	+	—	—	—	+	—	—	—
Tyrosine	1.40	1.25	1.63	1.00	0.55	1.11	0.90	0.71	1.02
Valine	2.05	2.81	2.34	2.14	3.11	1.32	2.70	2.44	1.66

Seeds* : 1. *Cassia fistula* 2. *Cassia occidentalis* 3. *Cassia tora*
4. *Indigofera glandulosa* 5. *I. hirsuta* 6. *I. trifoliata*
7. *Mucuna capitata* 8. *M. prurita* 9. *Trigonella occulta*.

** Optical density measured at 470 nm.

trisaccharides by their partial hydrolysis in presence of mineral salts of seed origin. The slight increase of reducing values at 100° could also be explained by the release of reducing sugars by hydrolysis of polysaccharides. Although the nature of residual reducing substances is not very clear, the free amino acids, ascorbic acid and carbohydrates with potential aldo and keto groups appear to be the main reducing substances present in seeds. In addition flavonoids, alkaloids, leucoanthocyanines and other seed pigments possessing phenolic properties as referred by Bate-Smith and Lerner¹⁶ and Hegnaur¹⁷ could be the other contributing factors.

Each seed has its own pattern of amino acids and no single seed is found to be complete in itself with respect to the essential amino acids. The total number of amino acids varies from 9-13 (Table 3). The total free amino acids content of the seeds varies in the order of 0.21-0.50 g (in terms of glycine) per 100 g of dry seed powder (Table 3). The wide variation in the total free amino acid content could be attributed to the various stages of maturity of the seeds at the time of their collection and also to the rate of protein synthesis during seed ripening. Although the seeds are wild, uncultivated and go waste but all the seeds examined could be considered as efficient source of carbohydrate and proteins from the nutritional point of view, if those that are incomplete with respect to certain essential amino acids are supplemented with missing essential amino acids.

Acknowledgement

The author (S. K. K.) wishes to thank the University Grants Commission for financial assistance.

References

1. W. C. ROSE, *Federation Proc.*, 1949, **8**, 546.
2. O. E. TREVELYN and J. S. HARRISON, *Biochem. J.*, 1952, **50**, 293.
3. P. B. HAWK, B. L. OSER and W. H. SUMMERSON, *Pract. Physiol. Chem.*, 12th Edn. Churchill, London, 1954, p. 577.
4. G. H. HOWDEN and B. A. KILBY, *J. Insect. Physiol.*, 1960, **4**, 258.
5. R. CONSDEN, A. H. GORDON and A. J. P. MARTIN, *Biochem. J.*, 1944, **38**, 224.
6. S. M. PARTRIDGE, *Nature*, 1949, **164**, 443.
7. S. P. DATTA, C. E. DENT and H. HARRIS, *Science*, New York, 1950, **112**, 620.
8. J. J. PRATT and J. L. AUCLAI, *Science*, New York, 1948, **108**, 213.
9. D. MUTING, *Naturwissenschaften*, 1952, **39**, 303.
10. I. SMITH, *Nature*, 1953, **171**, 42.
11. R. J. BLOCK, H. M. WINEGARD and G. TOERNIES, *Science*, 1948, **108**, 506.
12. S. S. SAKAGUCHI, *J. Biochem.*, Tokyo, 1925, **5**, 25.
13. R. PANT, H. C. AGRAWAL, *Naturwissenschaften*, 1963, **50**, 530.
14. H. ROSEN, *Arch. Biochem. Biophys.*, 1957, **67**, 10.
15. G. S. NIRANJAN and S. K. KATIYAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 822.
16. E. C. BATE-SMITH and N. H. LERNER, *Biochem. J.*, 1954, **58**, 126.
17. R. HEGNAUR, *Arzneipflanzen-Umschau*, 1956, **5**, 638.